

Performance Analysis of QS-CDMA Systems

Cuiran Li, Jianli Xie, and Chengshu Li

Abstract—In the paper, the performance of quasi-synchronous CDMA (QS-CDMA) system, which can allow an increased timing error in synchronized access, is discussed. Average BER performance of the system is analyzed in the condition of different access timing error and different asynchronous users by simulation in AWGN channel. The results show that QS-CDMA system is shown to have great performance gain over the asynchronous system when access timing error is within a few chips and asynchronous users is tolerable. However, with access timing error increasing and asynchronous users increasing, the performance of QS-CDMA will degrade. Also, we can determine the number of tolerable asynchronous users for different access timing error by simulation figures.

Keywords—Code-division multiple access, Quasi-Synchronous CDMA, Access timing error

I. INTRODUCTION

CODE-division-multiple-access (CDMA) communication systems have attractive features, such as antijam resistance, low probability of interception, resistance to multipath fading and capability of random access, which have been widely researched. The capability of random access, namely asynchronous CDMA (A-CDMA) system makes the inference of Multi-Access Interference (MAI) and Far-Near effect very serious. To solve this problem, synchronous CDMA (S-CDMA) has been proposed; in which users have access synchronously. Compared with A-CDMA, S-CDMA shows good performance as far as the perfect synchronization is fulfilled. This perfect synchronization, however, is very difficult to implement, which often occurred in the reverse link. Based on these, Quasi-Synchronous CDMA (QS-CDMA) is proposed, in which allows a certain amount of access timing error in the synchronization^[1-9].

The paper analyzes the performance of QS-CDMA system in AWGN channel. The results show that the performance of QS-CDMA system is close to that of S-CDMA when access timing error is within a few chip and asynchronous users is tolerable. This paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the QS-sequence and evaluates the performance. Section III give the simulation results. Conclusions are drawn

Manuscript received July11, 2005. This work was supported by Nation Science Foundations of China under Grant 60372093 and Research Foundations of Northern JiaoTong University under Grand 2003RC051.

Cuiran Li is with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Northern JiaoTong University, Beijing, China (phone: 86-10-58022888-201; fax: 86-10-58022066; mail: xie_jianli@grandi.cn; xjl@sina.com).

Jianli Xie is with the Embedded Software Division, Grand Digital Information LTD., Beijing, China. (e-mail: xie_jianli@grandi.cn).

Chengshu Li is with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Northern JiaoTong University, Beijing, China (e-mail: csli@center.njtu.edu.cn).

in Section IV.

II. QS-SEQUENCE AND PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

This section deals with the performance evaluation of the QS-CDMA system in terms of BER. The performance of QS-CDMA is strongly dependent on the signature sequences^[7]. Let QS-sequence be defined as the spreading sequences which allow a certain amount of access timing error. To reduce multi-user interference in the presence of access timing error, cross-correlation of QS-sequences should be kept minimum within a certain chips. The set of sequences which has a large range of minimum cross-correlation and has a large family of the sequence, are optimal for QS-sequences. In this paper, the QS-sequences selected from m-sequences and Walsh-codes are discussed, and average BER in the presence of access timing error in AWGN channel is evaluated by simulation.

We first select a set of QS-sequences for the case of m-sequences. In simulation, we produce m-sequence of length 31, and every cyclic phase shift 3chips is assigned to each user, which are shown as

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= \{PN_1, PN_2, PN_3, PN_4, \dots, PN_{31}\}; \\ C_2 &= \{PN_4, PN_5, \dots, PN_{31}, PN_1, PN_2, PN_3\}; \\ &\vdots \\ C_6 &= \{PN_{16}, PN_{17}, \dots, PN_{31}, PN_1, PN_2, \dots, PN_{15}\}; \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

We then select a set of QS-sequences for the case of Walsh-codes. In simulation, we produce Walsh-codes of length 32 which is denoted as $W_i(t)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 32$, and choose six Walsh-codes randomly for six users.

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= \{W_1, W_2, W_3, W_4, \dots, W_{32}\}; \\ C_2 &= \{W_3, W_4, \dots, W_{32}, W_1, W_2\}; \\ &\vdots \\ C_6 &= \{W_{11}, W_{12}, \dots, W_{32}, W_1, \dots, W_{10}\}; \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The BER performances of QS-CDMA in the condition of different access timing error and different asynchronous users are shown in Fig.1-6. For comparisons, the performance of S-CDMA and A-CDMA is analyzed in Ref.[10]. For S-CDMA system, the ratio of signal power and noise power is written as

$$SNR_{S-CDMA} = \frac{2E_b}{N_0} \quad (3)$$

and bit-error-rate can be expressed by

$$BER_{S-CDMA} = Q\left(\sqrt{\frac{2E_b}{N_0}}\right) \quad (4)$$

where

$$Q(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_x^\infty e^{-(y^2/2)} dy \quad (5)$$

For A-CDMA system, the ratio of signal power and noise power is given by

$$SNR_{A-CDMA} = \left[\frac{N_0}{2E_b} + \frac{K-1}{3N} \right]^{-1} \quad (6)$$

and and bit-error-rate can be obtained as

$$BER_{A-CDMA} = Q \left(\sqrt{\left[\frac{N_0}{2E_b} + \frac{K-1}{3N} \right]^{-1}} \right) \quad (7)$$

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we study the performance of the QS-CDMA system by simulating the BER vs. SNR. The BER performances for different access timing error and different asynchronous users are shown in Fig. 1-Fig. 6.

From Fig.1 and Fig.2, It is observed that the performance of QS-CDMA will degrade with access timing error increasing on the condition of one asynchronous user. We also see that the scope of tolerable access timing error for m-sequence is much larger than for Walsh code, the latter is just within 0.2chip or so.

From Fig. 3-Fig. 6, It is observed that when access timing error is constant, the performance of QS-CDMA will degrade with asynchronous user increasing. In Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, for the case of access timing error 0.2 chip, the number of tolerable asynchronous users reaches to half of the active users when m-sequence is used, and more than half of the active users when Walsh-code is used. For the case of access timing error 0.5 chip shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6, the number of tolerable asynchronous users is still remain half of the active users for m-sequence and no user is tolerable for Walsh-code. That is, when access timing error is small (less than 0.2 chip), Walsh-code is preferable for spreading code, whereas with access timing error increasing m-sequence is good choice.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we analyze the performance of QS-CDMA system in AWGN channel. The result shows that when access timing error is small (less than 0.2chip), Walsh-code is preferable for spreading code, whereas with access timing error increasing m-sequence is a good choice.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.Onan, O. Kucur, and E. Ozturk, "Performance of quasi-synchronous scale-time-code division multiple access system over the additive white Gaussian noise channel", IEEE Signal Processing and Communications Applications Conference, pp.708-711, April 2004.
- [2] A. Kuramoto, T. Abrao, and P. J. Jeszensky. "Sets of sequences for QS-CDMA systems with interference cancellation over multipath Rayleigh fading channels", IEEE Eighth International Symposium on Spread Spectrum Techniques and Applications, pp.694-698, Sep. 2004.
- [3] J. K. Kyeong, R. A. Iltis, "Joint detection and channel estimation algorithms for QS-CDMA signals over time-varying channels", IEEE Trans.on Commun., Vol.50, pp. 845-855, May 2002.
- [4] S. Cioni, G. D. Gaudenzi, and R. Rinaldo, "Adaptive coding and modulation for the reverse link of broadband satellite networks", IEEE GLOBECOM '04, Vol.2, pp. 1101-1105, Dec. 2004.

Fig. 1 BER comparison of different access timing error for m-sequence (under 1 asynchronous user)

Fig. 2 BER comparison of different access timing error for Walsh code (under 1 asynchronous user)

- [5] F. Pingzhi, "New direction in spreading sequence design and the related theoretical bounds", IEEE International Conference on Communications, Circuits and Systems and West Sino Expositions, Vol.1, pp. xliiii - xlvi, July 2002
- [6] S. H. Duan. "Researches on Quasi-Synchronous CDMA and Its Application in Mobile Satellite Communication System". Harbin Industry University, 2001.
- [7] L. Biqi; Z. Ping, H.Jiandong, "A generalized QS-CDMA system and the design of new spreading codes", IEEE Trans.on VTC, Vol. 47, pp.12687-1275, Nov.1998
- [8] S. Stanczak, A. Feistel, "Dynamic resource allocation for frequency-selective orthogonal QS-CDMA channels", IEEE Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers, Vol. 1, pp.632-636.2004
- [9] J. K. Kyeong, R. A. Iltis, "Block coded modulation for the QS-CDMA system", IEEE Conference on Signals, Systems and Computers, Vol. 1, pp.9-12, Nov. 2003
- [10] D. V. Sarwate, "Mean-Square Correlation of Shift-Register Sequence", IEE Proceedings.1984,131(2):101-106.

Fig. 3 BER comparison of different asynchronous users for m-sequence (within 0.2 chip access timing error)

Fig. 6 BER comparison of different asynchronous users for Walsh code (within 0.5 chip access timing error)

Fig. 4 BER comparison of different asynchronous users for Walsh code (within 0.2 chip access timing error)

Fig. 5 BER comparison of different asynchronous users for m-sequence (within 0.5 chip access timing error)